

Sociological Upshot of Social Communications on the Academic Performance of Sociology Students at University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College

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Abstract

The nucleus of the sociological research was to dictate the ramifications of the utilization of social communications sites on the academic performance of sociology students at Fourah Bay College, University of Sierra Leone. Social communications is a renowned mode for communication amongst university sociology students in Sierra Leone. Nonetheless, extreme social communications utilization, markup inquiries about whether academic performance is affected. This sociological research explores this inquiry by directing a sociological research on Fourah Bay College, University of Sierra Leone, sociology students, in evaluates to social communications handling and their academic performance. The sociological research also explored which social web is the most renowned amongst Sierra Leone university sociology students, why sociology students visit their social communications sites and if there exist considerable upgrade in the sociology student academic performance. Survey was utilized as a mechanism for information crowding. The sociological research welcomed 30 feedbacks and expressive social statistics involving commonality trials that is dissipate threads were utilized to explore the social network between the midpoint digit of hours students consumed of social communications a week and the merits they obtain from utilizing social communications sites. The social communications sites expressly Google +, Facebook, WhatsApp, Skype and X former Twitter grab the focus of sociology students for sociological research and affecting certainly their academic Grade points. The disclosures of the sociological research can be utilized to initiate the appropriate social schemes for upgrading the academic performance of sociology students in this fashion that a steadiness in the inactivity, particulars social reciprocity and academic performance can be preserved.

Keywords: *Sociological Upshot, Communications, Academic Performance, Sociology Students, Fourah Bay College.*

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Introduction

The ramifications of social communications on the academic performance of sociology students at Fourah Bay College has become a manifestation of lofty uncertainties and this is object immensely much frequent among sociology students at Fourah Bay College. This is an affair or obstacle that retains on upsetting virtually commonplace and it is the predominant.

The swift advancement of information communication automations in the previous decades has reformulated the patterns of instructing and erudition in higher education. Social communications became a significant part of human existence, already the exceptional or utilizations of network in numerous segment of human social existence.

Social communications inspires the community's engagement unfavorably additionally undoubtedly, as it becomes an immense occurrence to be females and males because social communications is cordial, efficient, systematic and simple to utilize. Currently, many students most mainly sociology students at Fourah Bay College are utilizing social communications as a global instrument for cohort presentations or dialogues, lecture drill interchange and social communications. The presence of elegant gadgets like laptops, tablets, phones and other gadgets uplifted the craving to utilize social communications as a commonplace practice in the student's social existence; because of this craving influences sociology students existence, communication and even personality-theories.

Bearing in mind social communications is holistically utilized numerous social researchers have investigated the footprint of it on students performance some researchers appraised that daily university sociology students are spending between 8-10 hours on social communications engagements like browsing, posting, liking. According to the foregoing research social communications and its impression on students accomplishment and Grade Points Average's took significant focus from the sociological researcher. 2023 sociological research depicts that 90% of young adults who are university sociology students are utilizing Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, and X commonplace. When surveyed most sociology students returned the grounds for their capability to utilize multiple tasks concurrently to their thriving automation (WhatsApp and university lecture assignment) touching reproachfully to the academic upshots. Nonetheless, other sociological researchers stipulated a reproachful impression on students' performance with the prevalence of social communications elucidated that Facebook is one of the most accomplish platforms it attains to be the most utilized in universities that assisted in distributing social intellect and particulars many lecturers adopt it as a social communication instrument by generating social instrument to bolster the lecture hall thoughts and discourses.

Social communications is commenced when folks commence to communicate. Social means human society, as involvement of renown and the cohorts and vocable communications is the avenue of social articulation. Most of the structures of social communications are not digital it generates a substantial digit of transformations and social communications is one of the colossal devising of automations, which is now folks and globally utilized.

Sociological researchers interpret social communications as automations that made social communication effortless and warrant conversations among its social participants. While in this sociological research the vocable social communications means a web situated mobile application that all manufacturers or establishments to assemble, associate with, and distribute contemporary customers developed or modern

stuff in digital social domain. Sociology students are clients and internet of communications. Gratitude to the internet and social web involving X, Facebook, Smartphones, WhatsApp, blogs and text messaging most sociology students progressively exist in a social sphere where sociological data is access to communication automations for instance, there are 4.8 billion social communications customers globally, constituting 59.9% of the universal social community and 92.7% of all internet customers (Nyst, 2023). 90.93% have a cell phone (Bmc, 2023) and 87 % have a smart phone (Bmc, 2023).

Sociology students are not always possessing communications proficiency expertise that can assist them to diligently explored, comprehend and appraise contemporary constructions of social data and make intelligent resolutions about its standard and operations (Zachlod et al, 2022) the utilization of social communication has become extensive and presently the most renowned social communications platforms and WhatsApp, Facebook, LinkedIn, Skype, Google +, MySpace, X, and smart phones. Facebook users profiles permits the user to convey social particulars with each other and permitted the user to construct and preserve social network and uplifted members to be a part of a community among students of colleges online social websites become renowned in the final previous years. Social communications is utilized to link with tertiary education students increasing responded (Williams, 2023). This in turn put constraint on members of the faculty of social sciences to utilize social networking within the classrooms and outside to link with sociology students. It is utilized to augment reasoning and construction of communication. Sociological research is done in which graduate seminar is connected for sociology students in classroom discourse phases. WhatsApp and Facebook are utilized by sociology students to connect with each other.

An accomplished 132 sociology students that check on the students engagement and social communications on the grades of students. They made dual cohorts of sociology students; one cohort do not utilized WhatsApp and the other cohort utilizes it. Students utilize WhatsApp to converse the study material, connect with classmates, and organized study cohorts. The sociological researcher with his co-workers comes to comprehend that students utilize WhatsApp had excellent Grade Points Averages and impressive results as compare to another cohort.

The conception of smart phones has augmented the conduct of social communications. It enables users to approach numerous social relating sites via just few clicks. Social communications has a broader impression on students on which vast digit of researches has been conducted and each social research depicts distinctive outcomes, some sociological researches manifest that social communications reproachfully influence the performance of students while according to some researchers it upgrades the social education of its users and enhance their social communication dexterity.

The universe is today honoring the advancement of communication automation which has amplified the purview of social communication via data social communication automations. Modern automation in communication no hesitation has transformed the whole universe into a "Macrocosm Hamlet". But as it is, automation like dual edges of the coin, escort with it both gloomy and productive edges. It assists folks to be exceptional acquainted, educated and assisting familiar with global growth. Automation exhibits mankind to exceptional path doing stuffs social networking sites contains Yahoo Messenger, iPhone and Android Facebook, BlackBerry messenger, X, Facebook messenger, BlackBerry messenger, WhatsApp messenger go messenger,.

These social networking sites are utilized by most global folks to interact with physical or internet friends, current and aging friends (Tafesse, 2022). The globe has been transformed swiftly by the emergence of automation; this has panned out into the utilization of automation as the outstanding norm to delve into expansive stretch of social education.

The progression of internet automation has led to its utilization has the finest social norm of communication whereby dual-third of the globe's internet community visits social blogging sites or social networking sites, consequently performing as an affinity and communication instrument. Social networking sites are online communities of internet users who want to communicate with other users about social spaces of collective enthusiasm, whether from an intimate pursuit or scholarly context (Haili and Wu, 2020).The millions of social networking sites have metamorphosed the reflection of global hamlet into a factuality whereby billions of folks connect or correspond via social networking sites.

The utilization of social communications between students has attained lofty thresholds and has overwhelmed their study moment, wrong spellings and poor grammar when socializing on social communications as well as distracting their focus from their studies. Students spent much of their moment on social networks than their educational efforts and it has touched their grade point average in terms of educational performance (Kolhar et al, 2021).

Several of the most renowned social communications websites are Facebook (and its associated Facebook messenger) WhatsApp, X, Wikia, MySpace, Snap chart. Google, MySpace, Instagram, We chart and LinkedIn. These social communications websites have more than 100,000,000 listed users. In America, a 2023 inquiry disclosed that 71% of teenagers have a Facebook account. Over sixty percent of thirteen to seventeen years old have at least one profile on social communications, with multiple expending further than two hours a day on social networking sites.

Theoretical Review

Theoretical review explores theories that expound on the topic under research and which, thereby assist in exceptional comprehension of the research in question while at the same time lodging forth a justification for the current social research. So, notwithstanding the following are the theoretical review been postulated in this sociological research by divergent sociological researchers.

Recurrently the previous decade, the globe has affirmed an enormous augment in the residence of social communications automations (Graf, 2023). A complementary experience has been attested regarding social communication's upshots on student moment, materials, and self-assertion. The globe has encountered a reevaluation of contemporary social constructions and a stretch of platforms bolstering up those structures. In an instructional backdrop, social communications questions orthodox suppositions that have extensive distinguished the social education experience of all students (Yap et al, 2022). Expired are the days of solitary transmission related to broadcasting (Zhang and Duan, 2022), for in the age of social communications, transmission is a dual path, thrice path, and centenary path instrument that is communal, captivating, and predominant. In this communal social communications globe, the approach of social knowledge concept submits a privilege to advance leaps in student accomplishment, as comprehensible theories of social focus, recollection,

and inspiration (Cilliers, 2021) are emboldened by social communications. Correspondingly, these attributes are predominantly sustainable via social communications, augmenting comprehensible procedures linked with social education and learning actualization.

Of the modifiable influencing whether a recognized social education hallmark or attribution of cognition is embodied by a student, focus is one most influenced by a person's features of receptive competence, excitement threshold, constant location, and prior support. If a social education engagement is to be accomplished, it must accommodate to one or more of a student's subjective traits of grasp. For instance, lecturers often pursue procedures for documenting presence in the conventional lecture room. If a student's intuitive situation or intuitive contemplation is coordinated such that listening to his or her name picks them to focus. It can be resolved that a positive threshold of focus is endorsed by commencing a student's name when commitment is anticipated. Granted this instance, acknowledge the likelihood of the student being invited by hundreds of voices across a combined digital social space. In this path, social communications transcend in cultivating a focused relation between the student and the domain of accessible social knowledge, alarming the student back into the social education connection with each like and with each missive.

Social education concept furnishes a connection between the behaviorist perspective and the cognitive perspective to social education concept. With a consistent spring of data, it is not sufficient to simply give focus to the social context of knowledge. Factual social education demands outside enticement and bits of social data to be concealed into the student's recollection, able to be recaptured and adapted to outside existence circumstances. Social relation is an intricate structure of communal components, each operating a divergent social function that may or may not have an impact on permanent recollection. By affording intensifying motive in the design of vivid depictions, analysis through companion expositions, and the capability to relate with social data in a live environment, social communications boost student chances for recollection formulation and recollection custody.

Enclosed social learning theory schema for social education, identity capability recreates an essential task (Cilliers, 2021). A person's convictions about the impact he or she can have upon the globe are outstanding to conceiving that impact. In terms of social education, students are further probably to overwork resources toward accomplishing a social resultant if they trust in their own competence to accomplish that resultant. Acknowledge dual faculty university students at a fresher's jam: one with lofty identity competence, one with low identity-competence. Nonetheless both may eager to boogie; repealing sociological elements of identity-competence cause each to acknowledge the heeded impact that boogying may have upon social uprighting. Similar resemblance interprets to lecture hall social obligation and student accomplishment. If social education is principally a social attempt or strives, it is further probable to occur when sociological elements mandate that exhausting resources will result in a supportive aftermath.

Rational with extant sociological discourses, the connectivism concept convey presumptions that intensify comprehension of social and how it may be further generated in now automated globe (Cleary, 2021). The connectivism concept espouses how the internet is being strengthened by persons to educate and exchange social data across the globe, and prior sociological researches have entrenched that a prevailing online site is social communications (Harris, 2023). With the assist of

internet automations, social communications has become a significant social education instrument.

The Activity framework theory investigates social education as a social drill and enterprise or engagement (Carmago-Hendriquez, 2022) and can be adapted in drill. It portrays the social education ambience and scholarly blueprints (Miao and Ma, 2022) and situates importance on the environment of social learning and doing, instrument utilized and association, theme and background. Cultural Historical Activity Theory implies a linkage between theory and drill appearing in a historical and socio-cultural setting (Gormley et al, 2020) and addresses the lacuna between theory and drill by situating stuff, engagement before language and theory. Mogenic and others observe that humans require intervening relics to shift from diminished to Higher Cognitive Functions. Engagements are imperative for cognitive growth and cognitive talents advancement as an outcome of personalization of behaviors with objects and other folks and then exteriorization. The theory grants social education as both person and communal, metamorphosing each and every one (Mogenic et al, 2023). However, their theorization of educational drills or rehearsals, socio-historic reservations for construction of current social knowledge and contemporary drills are required (Lotan and Minkov, 2023). Consequently, social knowledge utilization demands a socially affluent domain.

The bedrock of social constructivism in the setting of social education was established on Vygotsky's work. He stressed the task of others, or the social setting, in social education and as a result, instructors were encouraged to revisit the threshold to which social education is a procedure restricted to the social individual or being. Furthermore challenged that the path between objects and reflection is arbitrated by other persons via language gestures and emblems. Human social history is constructed on man's expanding dominance over nature via the stepping of instruments and the completeness of automation, and on the other hand, man continuously cultivates personality-jurisdiction via involvement of cultural indicate modes. Besides, exaggerated culture and community by disputing that all more advanced intellectual social functions emanates from society and are interspersed in socio-cultural milieu.

Perceptive Sociological Education

Sierra Leone sociological education has felt its own savor of social communication subsequently its prologue. Social communication in Sierra Leone commenced as a snail pace procedure like other Mano River nations but has expanded gradually over the previous decades. According to the Statista, "the mobile phone subscriptions per 100 inhabitants in Sierra Leone are forecast to amount to 108.20 in 2023 and the telephone subscriptions per 100 inhabitants are forecast to amount 0.00 in 2023". Furthermore, the number of mobile data subscribers in the nation has augmented dramatically. Mobile data subscription for 2023 was 265.00k with a penetration rate of internet users to 2.87million. This indirectly means there will be further access to the internet which of course involves social networking sites. The inquiry conducted by Sengupta and Vaish (2023) classed utilisation of social media and its impacts on academic performance of tertiary students and from a global context revealed that majority of students in Sierra Leone were engrossed in social networking sites. It also brought to light that most users utilized these sites for chatting and downloading intents only which influenced their academic performance pessimistically. This finding

corroborates the revelation of Wu and Xin (2019) that most respondents in their inquiry experienced pessimistic impacts such as low enthusiasm for learning, lack of motivation and interest, weak willingness to learn and poor learning mentality. Nonetheless, part of these studies asserted some merits of social communication custom in the academic social existence of students. It is imperative as educators to be bothered about its pessimistic impact which imply to be outbalancing the merits as far as social education is concerned in Freetown, Sierra Leone. A review of extant literature has led to the authentication of the following elements as the pivotal considerations of student academic performance, expressly; performance during examinations, facilities, guidance, stress, negativity, upshot and impact.

Examination

Amran et al (2020) utilized Grade Point Average to assess student performance because their central focus was on student performance for a specific semester. Some other researchers utilized test or previous year result since they are studying performance for the particular discipline or year (Mickel, 2021). In holistic, performance during examinations has demonstrated to be the most renowned and dependable incentive of a student's academic performance.

Multiple studies have been analyzed with regard to the divergent elements that influence the students' academic performance. There are dual sorts of communication elements that influence the students 'academic performance. These are within and outside lecture room elements and these elements robustly influence the students' performance. Within classroom elements involve students' competence in Sociology, lecture schedules, lecture size, Sociology text and e-books, lecture test outcomes, social education facilities, assignment, environment of the lecture, complexity of the course material, lecturer's social function in the lecture room, automation utilized in the lecturer and exams systems. Outside lecture room elements involve extracurricular engagements, work and financial, family problems, social and other communal problems. If the students have robust communication expertise and have robust grip on Sociology, it augments the performance of the students. The performance of the student is influenced by communication expertise because it is possible for students to see social communication as a variable which may be confidently associated to performance of the student in e-learning. Assignment, environment of the lecture room, sophistication of the course material, lecturer's functional social function in the lecture room, automation utilized in the lecture room and examinations structures.

Facilities

Tadese et al (2022) discovered that student's performance is significantly associated with contentment with academic environment and the facilities of library, computer lab in the institution. With regard to background variables, they discovered a positive impress of high university performance and accomplishment but discovered no probability validation of compelling alliance between household earning threshold and academic performance of the student. Tadese et al (2022) concluded those "older students" of educational management should be highly educated in order to ensure that their influence on the divergent students they preside over is positive for the vocational and socio-psychological growth of the students. According to them, it is essential that is loftily essential for student learning. Josiah et al (2022) clenches the

glimpse that student performances are associated with the utilization of library and threshold of their University social education. Her social research divulged that the utilization of the library appreciatively influenced student performance. The academic community is an adequate adaptable for students and has a cogent expectant affinity with their grade threshold.

Guidance

Suleiman (2023) distinguished that students' academic accomplishments and engagements, insights of their surviving blueprints and cogent acknowledgements, and setting traits (household finance, parents threshold of social education, direction from parents and number of pessimistic circumstances in the domicile) were straightly linked to their academic accomplishments in high school. The students encounter several problems in evolving cogent study mindsets and study wont. Instruction is the element via which a student can enhance his study mindset and study wont and is straightly corresponding to academic success. The students who are suitably trained by their parents have performed well in the examinations. The instruction from the lecturer also influences the student performance. The training from the parents and the lecturers broadside the performance of the students.

Stress

Socio-economic elements like participation in the lecture, household income, and mother's and father's social education, presence of qualified and research oriented lecturer in the faculty, lecturer-student ratio, sex of student and distance of the university also influence the performances of students in their divergent departmental sociology modules. Academic accomplishment of a graduate student will be bolstered if the maximum hale associated restrictions are inadequate. There is a pessimistic network between university credit and stress but feeble social network between Grade Point Average and stress. The students' academic performance banks on a digit of socio-economic elements like students' participation in the lecture room, household finance, parent social education, lecturer student ratio, existence of qualified and research oriented lecturer in the faculty, distance of the University, and sex of the student. However, there is a pessimistic network between the household finance and students' performance focused on private universities in Sierra Leone.

Upshot

Consequently, via email and instant messaging, online social communities are established where a donation financial system and mutual generosity are inspired via collaboration. Google and other social networking instruments are progressively the design of scholarly sociological research. Scholars in many fields have begun to investigate the impact of social networking site, examining how such site may recreate into affairs of privacy, youth culture and social education, identity and privacy. Several websites are beginning to tap into the power of the social networking model for philanthropy. In 2023 Bhanye et al conducted research that depicted that social media is a "double edge sword" and time squandering but also have promoted student learning with a collective spring of information. In this perspective, when one is chit-chatting, the content of the message discloses a lot about a person. In comments,

status, photos, chatting and comments should speak less of a person. Jain et al (2023) in summary says: “There are numerous security and privacy issues related to the user’s shared information especially when a user uploads personal content such as photos, videos and audios”; and, in reference to this, Al-Rahmi et al (2022), states that “Social media utilisation at the student level has become more prevalent contemporary higher education, and have aligned expectation on performance and effort”. It is a whirlwind that absorb individuals in and individuals have no opinion they have been grabbed. One of the ironies of the internet is that it keeps individuals apart from the most significant stuffs. It is a great path to remain associated with folks but individuals just have to comprehend when to shut it down. However, Beyari (2023) emphasized that it seems that when youngsters go on a social network, they lose their mind which has a positive and negative impact.

Impact

The positive accomplishments of social communications has shifted to a divergent proportion since the inception of these social communications networks and various inquiries have maintained that social communications plays a significant social function on students in higher education involving the inquiry conducted by Capriotti and Zeeler (2023). In their social inquiry, they confirmed four notable merits of social communication custom by students in higher education which involved; upgrading relationship, perfecting knowledge incentive, contributing individualized course material, and advancing communal competences. Certainly, social communications has contributed immensely to expediting sociological education in the 21st century. It is depicted that a prime section of students involving those at the Master level typically utilized social communications to improve their social inquiries (Popescu and Badea, 2020). The responses to the roots of docile social inquiries presently around the universe might not be far-fetched from the immense contribution that social communications platforms are providing when utilized prudently or wisely. Nonetheless, there have been other school of thought that states that social communications is a creep to students academic social existence such as Kolhar et al (2021), they debated in their inquiry that social networks divert the focus or concentration of the students toward learning and converts it towards non-educational social engagements such as worthless and needless conversation, there have been various inquiries conducted afterwards whose findings are diametric to this assertion. For example, the inquiry conducted by Chen and Xiao (2022), titled “ The Effect of Social Media on The Development of Students Affective Variables” acknowledged the positive and negative impact of social media and that students profit from conversing with other students, lecturers and outside sources to obtain sociological education. Furthermore, Muftah (2022) debated in the similar path that students acquired more social dialect, enhanced their writing skills and mitigated their spelling errors and mistakes via social communications practice. Absolutely, as a sociological educational instrument, social communications perfects sociological learning by giving both students and lecturers the social privilege to associate in contemporary and very interesting paths thereby promising docile system of sociological education. It is mentioned that docile sociological education stretches the option on what, when and how folks educate. It bolsters divergent modes of sociological education including E-learning which profoundly patronized around the universe (Boe et al, 2021). Other social pundits; Gulzar al (2021), in their inquiry also disclosed that social communications profits students by associating them to one another on individual

inspiration, individual or group presentations, and ingenuity. It is further underpinned in the inquiry of KrutKa and Milton (2023) whose summaries were that social communications undeniably breed contemporary privileges to occupy students in higher sociological education as they are exceptionally efficient at associating folks and facilitating the trading of social enlightenment. It is obvious and irrefutable from these inquiries that social communications practice in the educational precinct cannot be undervalued since its prologue or inception.

Negativity

Marttila and Pekka (2021) itemized some of the perils connected with social communications which involved criminal engagements such as self-identity burglary and counterfeit connections which are prevalent today, bugging or carnal abuse and improper advertising. On the similar social theme Ademiluyi et al (2021), also revealed online harassment, cyber bullying, face book depression, sexting, and confidentiality troubles as some of the difficulties connected with social networking.

Cyber bullying is a sort of bullying that happens in the digital domain or sphere of electronic text. Ordinarily, it is any behavior performed through electronic or digital communications by individuals or cohorts that repeatedly communicates hostile or aggressive messages intended to inflict harm or discomfort on other persons (Al-Turif and Al-Sunad, 2023). Cyber bullying is one the grave risk in the social communications community and has called for a number of inquiries to actuate its inducements. The inducements of cyber bullying according to Lam et al (2022) , was significantly linked with the utilization of prescient defiance, justification of cruelty, vulnerability to violence and limited felt social reinforcement of colleagues.

This is another concern that everyone involved in social networking encountered with. The pace at which folks post or share counterfeit information request for panic and it is tricky to determine that, what folks utter, and post are frankly who they are. Individuals secrete or confidential information is publicly flashed on some of these social networks and vicious folks take merit and commit all sorts of bugging. It is also debated that the confidentiality alternatives offered by most social networking sites do not furnish customers or users with the flexibility required to manage confrontations with persons who have divergent impressions of confidentiality (Rossi et al 2022). Hence these consequences, other inquiries conducted by pundits have also substantiated that social communications can be injurious to students academic existence if prudence is not taken in its practice. For instance, the inquiry conducted by Attar et al. (2023), titled “Use of Social Media for the Improvement of Safety Knowledge and Awareness Among Saudi Arabian Phlebotomists” summarized that social communication influences or promotes security need on the use social communications. Sociology students use short handwriting when conversing with colleagues and unintentionally get utilized to it thereby reproducing same errors during examinations. Even though one may contend that these are slight difficulties, it is significant to accept the augmenting threshold at which these errors are reproduced in the education sector and if care is not taken eventual generation may see it as a social standard definitely to students involving but not restricted to the inquiry of Ramaraj (2020), Sharma and Behi (2022) and Adalakun et al (2023) among others have mentioned unquestionably that social communications can be thorny to students academic engagement or performance is not taken in its practice.

Methodology

Data gathering of this social research comprises of the structured dialogues for both female and males sociology students at the Department of Sociology and Social Work, University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College. The questions were designed in such a path that it was simple to gather quantitative data as well. The structured questionnaire utilized was pre-tested prior the actual data gathering engagement in order to examine for precision, evenness and unreliability. The data gathering instruments utilized in this research involved questionnaires, structured and unstructured dialogues plans in order to evaluate the impact of social communications sites in circumstances associated to students at the Department of Sociology and Social Work, Fourah Bay College. In order to establish the statistical data of this research, the manual lodged instruments such as computer lodged programs like Excel, calculator and other related programs were utilized. This sociological research focused on investigative work to find out the impacts of social communications sites on the student performance. An investigative research is a path of collecting social data by employing explicit observation. It is utilized to answer factual questions, which must be precisely interpreted and answerable with data. The target population in this research comprises sociology students in the Department of Sociology and Social Work, University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College.

Findings

Presuming the guidance network has regulating upshots on students' academic performance, then what are the implications for directive blueprint? A Web-based forum may provide an outstanding means of communication for students to connect with every one, a privilege to manifest them, and a setting with limited social problems, such as those associated with introversion.

Supposing sociological education is predominantly carved via interaction among students and between students and their social instructor, then interactions among students should be robustly encouraged. Then, a Web-based forum may furnish students a discipline where they can openly talk over, pose questions or qualms, provide social thoughts, and comprehend after lecture.

There are multiple modes that can bolster online trainee's social interactions, such as facility of a debatable theme or issue for arguing or structuring a discussion. Some heated arguments (such as WhatsApp hacking, expensive restaurants and others) transpired in this sociological research during some weeks. Invigorating students' social interaction and accommodating germane feedback may become a lecturer's central responsibilities.

Subsequent work should concentrate on the blueprint and oversight of education social systems in a path that foster network growth. For instance, it is significant to comprehend what should be involved in a lecture room discourse and what should be left or extended to the forum. The future challenge will be how to formulate divergent instruction and discussion sessions online and offline in order to completely leverage the merits of students social networks.

Recommendations

The oversight or operation of University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College, should ensure that students with phones having internet social space are encouraged to either utilizing it to complement their research in the library rather than the accustomed conversation with friends all the moment.

Nonetheless, students should be advised by the oversight or operation of University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College to restrict the moment they devote on social communications sites daily and inspire them to rather replace those hours to read novels and relevant academic books to upgrade their education.

Subsequently the sociological research confirmed that the utilization of social communication sites had influenced the academic performance of students unfavorably, there is the urgent demand for the oversight or operation of University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College to initiate modes of how students will obtain books and other information means or materials in the library that can assist them educationally.

The oversight or operation of University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College should advise students during orientation on the risks of fixation to social networking sites. They should be introduced to sites that can attach merits to their educational task and social research.

Instead of restricting access to internet social spaces the librarians and oversight or operation of University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College should guide students on how to engage cleverly, decently and securely.

Conclusion

The sociological research gives the educational and confirming information. In current years, utilization of social communications has become very renowned all around the globe due to appreciable growth of automation. Apart from superstars but social commonality has also turned out to be a massive customer of these social communications sites. The fundamental intent behind conducting this study was to see the academic outcome of student who devote most of their time on such social interacting sites. The findings from conducted researches has find out to be predominantly constructive because students devote moment of their day engagements on these social communication sites have been able to share and accomplish contemporary notions and theories associated to their researches. They also utilize these sites for having fun as these social websites are beneficent in their academic work. Utilization of these interacting social communications has become the pattern or practice of student they devote the vital part of their moment on these sites for amusement and also focus on their studies. Students are a valuable social capital or strength of any nation. Via these social websites they do their academic work with passion. The sociological research was conducted to investigate the impact of students utilization of social communication sites on their academic performance. The sociological research disclosed that majority of the respondents had cellular phones with internet social space and had education of the prevalence of social communications sites. As a result they visit their social communications sites and devote between thirty minutes to three hours daily. In addition, the sociological research disclosed that the utilization of social communications had influenced academic performance of the respondents unfavorably and further confirmed that

there was a robust positive relationship between the utilization of social communication and academic performance.

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